

Development of a Flexible Technique for RF Welding of Innovative Recyclable Mono-Material Packaging Films

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A capacitive high frequency technology has been developed for the welding of innovative recyclable mono-material packaging films. Compared to established methods where heat is applied externally to the packaging material, this high-frequency technology offers short process times and is independent of thermal conductivity parameters and film thicknesses. This allows for an effective and high-quality processing of mono-layer films. However, many packaging materials based on polyolefins, such as Polyethylene or Polypropylene, exhibit insufficient dielectric properties, with a loss tangent $\tan(\delta) < 0.001$.

To address the limitations of conventional materials, a high frequency technology with adjustable frequency in the form of a packaging demonstrator (Fig. 1) has been developed. This system is suitable for novel mono-materials and offers several advantages such as high seam strengths, minimal structural impact on the materials being joined and homogeneous heating across the entire joining surface.

Additionally, a ϵ_r - $\tan(\delta)$ test setup was developed (Fig. 2). Using the COMSOL Multiphysics RF module, the setup was simulated and the relative permittivity (ϵ_r) and loss tangent ($\tan(\delta)$) was calculated by analyzing S-parameters across a frequency sweep. Mono-packaging materials based on Polyethylene were also developed and enhanced with varying proportions of vinyl acetate co-polymers to improve the welding suitability of conventional materials.

Fig. 1. Sealing demonstrator front view with sealing unit

Fig. 2. Illustration of the developed ϵ_r - $\tan(\delta)$ test set

Experimental validation was performed by measuring the foil's dielectric response using an RF test fixture and a vector network analyzer. The results from simulation and experiment are compared to ensure accuracy and material consistency. Finally, experiments were conducted using these packaging materials on the demonstrator. Quality tests of the seals, such as t-peel-tests and leakage tests, were performed to evaluate the effectiveness of the technology.